

A STUDY ABOUT THE EFFECTIVENESS OF HEALTH, YOGA AND SPORTS RELATED ACTIVITIES ON B.ED. TEACHER –TRAINEES

Dr. Kiran V. Nanaware

Associate Professor, Abhinav Education Society's, College of Education, Ambegaon Bk., Pune – 411046 E-mail Id: kvnabhinavbedcollege@gmail.com

Ms. Minal T. Sonukale

Assistant Professor, Abhinav Education Society's, College of Education, Ambegaon Bk., Pune – 411046 E-mail Id: minal.urade@gmail.com

Paper Received On: 20 MAY 2025

Peer Reviewed On: 24 JUNE 2025

Published On: 01 JULY 2025

Abstract

“Your body hears everything that, your mind says!” this quote reflects the importance of our mind and body co-relation. The great Philosopher, Aristotle said that, the Sound mind... is in our Sound body...! The focus or objectives of this study is on the development of knowledge, understanding, skills and attitude among the B.Ed. Students about the importance of Health, Yoga and Sports in our life. As well as, a today's Teacher- trainees are tomorrows nation builders... They should know very well about the need, importance, types, core characteristics, differences between health, sports and yoga activities. Teacher -trainees should know about how to do or conduct these activities as a teacher in the schools and in their own life also. The Objectives of this research as mentioned above, Researcher has used Experimental Research Method to check the effectiveness of these activities included in the SPPU B.Ed. Syllabus under the course code No. 112 i.e. Health & Yoga. The Randomized -lottery Sampling method was chosen by the researcher and Single Group – Pre & Post Test - Research design was used for this Research. The Teacher training colleges affiliated under the Savitribai Phule Pune University are the population of this research and the 50 students of the one teacher training college were the Sample of this study. For data collection researcher has used a questionnaire for it as a Pre and Post Test. The mean, average, median, Standard- Deviation, Co-relation and the 't'- Test was used to analyse the collected data by researcher. The Findings and the conclusion are mentioned at the end of this research paper, and it shows that, the implementation of Health, yoga & sports related activities made progress and a positive effects among the B.Ed. Teacher –trainees achievements.

Keywords: *Effectiveness, Health, Yoga, Sports, Activities, Teacher-trainees*

Introduction:

Healthy citizens are the greatest asset of any country. The role of parents, society, schools and Government is very important to achieve this goal. India is now a largest populated country in the world. Out of 140 Corer populations how much population is Skill- full and Healthy in the manner of mental and physical. i.e. the matters in the growth of our nation. Here not only the economic growth is expected but also, peace, non-violence etc... *Mahatma Gandhi Said that,*

“It is health that is real wealth and not pieces of gold and silver.”

– *M.K. Gandhi*

The health, yoga, and sports related activities are making the crucial role for physical and mental well-being, playing a vital role in overall health and quality of life. Yoga and sports offer numerous benefits, including improved physical fitness, reduced stress, enhanced mental clarity, and increased self-confidence. Incorporating these practices into daily routines can lead to a more balanced and fulfilling life.

Importance of Health, Yoga & Sports Activities in our life:

- Physical Well-being
- Physical Fitness
- Disease Prevention
- Stress Relief
-
- Mental Acuteness
- Social Benefits
- Mental Benefits
- Mind-Body Connection

Importance of Yoga:

Yoga improves flexibility, muscle strength, balance, posture, and cardiovascular health. It promotes relaxation, stress reduction, improved focus and concentration, and increased self-awareness. By doing Yoga, it emphasizes the connection between the mind and body, allowing for a holistic approach to well-being.

Importance of Sports Activities:

Sports provide a great way to build cardiovascular fitness, strength, and endurance, while also promoting teamwork and social interaction. Participating in sports releases endorphins, which have mood-boosting and stress-reducing effects. It requires focus, concentration, and problem-solving skills, enhancing cognitive function. Sports provide opportunities to socialize, build relationships, and develop leadership skills.

Adopting a healthy lifestyle that incorporates yoga and sports activities can significantly improve physical and mental well-being, promoting a more balanced and fulfilling life.

Role of Schools and Educational Institutions:

Educational Institutions, play a crucial role in promoting health, sports, and yoga by integrating these activities into the curriculum and offering various opportunities for physical activity and well-being. This includes structured physical education activities, classes, sports programs, and the introduction of yoga with mindfulness practices. By doing so, schools aim to cultivate healthy lifestyles, improve physical and mental well-being, and foster essential life skills in students.

Title of the Study:

Effectiveness of Health, Yoga and Sports related activities on of B.Ed. Teacher – trainees.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To Design the test to check the awareness, knowledge, understanding and skills among the Teacher -trainees.
2. To conduct the Pre - test and program based on the activities related to Health, Yoga and Sports.
3. To study the effectiveness about the Programme based on Health, Yoga & Sports related activities.
4. To collect, analyse, interpret the data with its findings and conclusions about the Test and programme based on activities related to Health, Sports and Yoga.

Definitions: (Conceptual & Operational)

Health: (Conceptual)

The World Health Organization (WHO) defines health as "a state of complete physical, mental, and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease or infirmity"

World Health Organization (WHO).

Health: (Operational)

The set of awareness - lectures & activities related to Health & Yoga planned, designed and conducted by Researcher with the help of Sports Director in Abhinav College of Education during the academic year 2024-2025 for B.Ed. First Year Students, as per the syllabus & guidelines given in the B.Ed. Syllabus by Savitribai Phule Pune University.

Yoga: (Conceptual)

Patanjali, in his Yoga Sutras, defines yoga as "Yogah citta-vrtti-nirodhah". This translates to "yoga is the cessation of the modifications of the mind". Essentially, yoga is a discipline that aims to quiet the mental chatter and fluctuations, allowing for a clearer and more focused state of being.

-Yog Guru Patanjali

Yoga: (Operational Definition):

The set of awareness - lectures & activities related to Health & Yoga planned, designed and conducted by Researcher with the help of Sports Director in Abhinav College of Education during the academic year 2024-2025 for B.Ed. First Year Students, as per the syllabus & guidelines given in the B.Ed. Syllabus by Savitribai Phule Pune University.

Sports: (Conceptual)

Sports are typically defined as physical activities or games, often competitive, that involve physical exertion and skill, governed by rules and often organized within a framework of institutions. Definitions may vary, with some emphasizing physical prowess and competition, while others include a broader range of physical activities for enjoyment and health benefits.

World Health Organization (WHO)

Sports: (Operational Definition):

The set of various Sports awareness - lectures, Competitions & activities planned, designed and conducted by Researcher with the help of Sports Director in Abhinav College of Education during the academic year 2024-2025 for B.Ed. First Year Students, as per the syllabus & guidelines given in the B.Ed. Syllabus by Savitribai Phule Pune University.

Programme: (Operational Definition):

A set of Lectures, Orientations, Workshops and Activities related to Health, Yoga and Sports competitions with achievement Tests which is conducted through-out the Academic Year of 2024-2025.

Effectiveness: (Conceptual Definition)

It's an assessment, whether research is effective, simply means finding out if it produced any outputs, outcomes and/or societal benefits or impact. The main unit of analysis required is simply a measure of outputs (or outcomes and/or impact).

Effectiveness: (Operational Definition):

The operational term effectiveness as per this research is, the difference between the performance of Health, Yoga and Sports activities, and mean score of Pre and Post Test es conducted among the B.Ed. Teacher-trainees of Abhinav B.Ed. First Year Students admitted in academic Year 2024-2025.

A Study: (Conceptual Definition)

The term "study" functions both as a noun and a verb, encompassing various meanings related to learning, examination, and research or a complete investigation and analysis of a subject, phenomenon, etc. – Britannica Dictionary

Assumptions:

1. Yoga, Health and sports inherently lead to improved physical health.
2. Yoga, Health and sports reduce stress and improve mental well-being.
3. Yoga, Health and sports improve athletic performance.
4. Adopting these activities as part of a daily routine will automatically lead to a healthier lifestyle.
5. Yoga, Health and sports are universally beneficial and suitable for everyone.
6. The conduction of Activities about Health, Yoga and Sport throughout First year B.Ed. Course in affiliated Colleges, as per the syllabus of Savitribai Phule Pune University, it enhances the knowledge, understanding, skills and develop the attitude, interest among the Teacher -trainees.
7. The awareness lectures, health, Yoga & Sports Competitions, activities improve the performance, knowledge, Understanding, Skills, attitude and Intrests of Teacher-trainees.
8. The activities conducted through out the Research duration can develop & improve the performance of Health, Yoga and Sports activities.

Hypothesis:

- i) **H₁: Research Hypothesis:** Teacher -trainees, who participate in all activities related to Health, Yoga & Sports through-out the year, will perform effectively Physical, oral and Written Test.
- ii) **H₀: Null Hypothesis:** There is no difference between the Teacher -trainees, who participate and doesn't participate in all activities related to Health, Yoga & Sports through-out the year, will perform effectively Physical, oral and Written Test.

Scope of the Study:

The present study was conducted on the B.Ed. Teacher- trainees, those who enrolled in the academic year 2024-2025 in First year of Abhinav College of Education, Ambegaon Bk., Pune.

Limitations of the Study:

1. The Psychological aspects like attention, motivation, interest are beyond the control of Researcher.
2. The effect in achievement and performance due to personal guidance and coaching will not be considered.
3. The difference between the efforts taken by teachers may differ the achievement or performance.
4. The conclusion of the study will depend upon the analysis of the responses given by respondents.

Delimitations:

- 1.) This study is conducted only in Abhinav College of Education, Ambegaon Bk., Pune – 411046.
- 2.) The present study results are applicable to the 50 (Fifty) Teacher-trainees of First Year B.Ed. Course
- 3.) The present study is related to checking the achievement and Performance of 50 Teacher-trainees about the Health, Yoga & Sports.

Variables:

- a) Independent Variable:** The Teacher-trainees and the Program/Course related activities about Health, Yoga & Sports with its Orientations conducted with the help of Expertise.
- b) Dependent Variable:** Mean Score of Pre & Post-test conducted by the research to check the achievement and performance of B.Ed. teacher – trainees.
- c) Extraneous Variables:** Age of Teacher –trainees, Medium of Instructions, IQ of the Teacher –trainees, Content related to Health, Yoga & Sports and Time-table etc.

Research Method of the Study: For this Present study Researcher has used Experimental Research Method.

Research Design: Single Group Pre & Post – test Design has used.

Copyright © 2025, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

Research Method of the Study:

For this Present study Researcher has used Experimental Research Method.

Research Design:

Single Group Design – Pre & Post Test has used. (Experimental Research Method)

Population and Sampling:

Randomized – Lottery method sampling was adopted for the present study.

Population:

All the teacher-trainees admitted in the Teacher Training colleges in the academic year 2024-2025 for B.Ed. – General Course, affiliated under Savitribai Phule Pune University, is the population for the present study.

Sample:

50 teacher -trainees Out of 100 from Abhinav College of Education, Ambegaon Bk., Pune – 46 were selected as a sample by using Randomized -lottery method sampling was used.

Tools for Data Collection:

A questionnaire is developed by Researcher to study the achievement about the awareness, knowledge, understanding of Health, Yoga & Sports activities. It has contained 40 questions to check the depth knowledge, awareness and understanding of teacher -trainees about the Health, Yoga and various sports activities and its conduction. Also, the questionnaire checks the Do's and Don'ts, Prose and Corns, Rules and Regulations about Yoga, Health & Sports activities and its conduction as a participants and Future Teacher.

Statistical Tools:

Researcher has made use of Mean, Percentage, Standard Deviation, Correlation – Coefficient, 't'- Test from descriptive statistical tools.

Procedure of Research:

• **Administration of Pre & Post – Test:**

A pre-test questionnaire was given to the Teacher-trainees to check the current status about Health, Yoga, and Sports related concepts, conduction & Performance of activities, its conduction knowledge, understanding, awareness, attitude, aptitude and skills present among them, after that, the program was conducted and then the post-test was conducted on same class. All the instructions were given to teacher – trainees before the conduction of both tests, about how to solve the questionnaire. Hence, 50 Teacher-trainees were solved the pre & post -tests within 01 Hour.

Table No. 01

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the pre-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities.

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre-Test				Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre-Test			
S. No.	Obtained Marks in pre -test	No. of Students		S. No.	Obtained Marks in pre -test	No. of Students	
1	12	1		10	24	4	
2	13	1		11	25	5	
3	15	2		12	26	2	
4	16	2		13	27	3	
5	17	2		14	28	5	
6	19	1		15	29	7	
7	21	1		16	30	4	
8	22	3		17	31	1	
9	23	6					

Graph No. 01

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the pre-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities.

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Post Test

Observation & Data Interpretation:

It is observed that, the above Table & graph shows that, the teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the pre-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities. The scores are classified in seventeen numbers. Out of 40 Marks 50 teacher-trainees obtained Marks in above classified Nos.

As per, the above graph, it is showing that the Scores of Pre -Test out of the 40 Marks. The 50 teacher- trainees had solved this Test. According to the values are showing in the Graph Minimum 12 Marks are achieved by One teacher and Maximum score achieved 31 out of 40 Marks obtained by 01 Teacher-trainee, so the range of Marks achieved in this Test is 12 – 31.

On the basis of above graph, the 50 teacher – trainees Pre - test Scores are classified in 17 values, and its Mean score of is the 24.26.

Table No. 02

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the post-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities.

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Post Test

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre-Test			Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre-Test		
S. No.	Obtained Marks in post -test	No. of Students	S. No.	Obtained Marks in post -test	No. of Students
1	24	1	6	35	7
2	31	3	7	36	9
3	32	2	8	37	9
4	33	4	9	38	5
5	34	8	10	39	1

Graph No. 02

Teacher -trainees score frequency in Pre – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the post-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities.

Graph No. 02: Teacher -trainees score frequency in post – Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the post-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities.

Observation & Data Interpretation:

It is observed that, the above Table & graph shows that, the teacher -trainees score frequency in post– Test, based on the Obtained Scores in the post-test about the development of awareness through Health, Yoga and Sports related activities. The scores are classified in seventeen numbers. Out of 40 Marks of 50 teacher-trainees obtained Marks classified in above Nos. or categories/frequencies

As per, the above graph, it is showing that the Scores of Posts -Test out of the 40 Marks. The 50 teacher- trainees had solved this Test. According to the values are showing in the Graph Minimum 24 Marks are achieved by One teacher and Maximum score achieved 39 out of 40 Marks obtained by 01 Teacher-trainee, so the range of Marks achieved in this Test is 24 – 39.

On the basis of above graph, the 50 teacher – trainees Post - test Scores are classified in 10 values, and its Mean score of is the 35. 08.

Table No. 03:

The classification of the teachers - trainee’s achievements in Pre & Post test scores based on grades.

Gradation: Researcher has classified the Scores achieved by Teacher-trainees in the Post Test out of 40 Marks as below:

S. No.	Class Intervals	No. of Teacher – trainees (Pre – Test)	Percentag e (_ / 50 * 100)	No. of Teacher- trainees (Post Test)	Percentag e (_ / 50 * 100)	Remarks (Performance Level)	Grad e
1.	37-40	0	0.00%	16	32.00%	Excellent	O
2.	33-36	0	0.00%	28	56.00%	Good	A+
3.	29-32	12	24.00%	5	10.00%	Average	A
4.	25-28	15	37.50%	0	0.00%	Satisfactory	B
5.	0 to 24	23	57.50%	1	2.00%	Unsatisfactor y	C
Total No. of Respondent s		50	100.00%	50	100.00%		

Graph No. 03:

Teacher-trainees’ achievements in the Pre & Post Test Scores classified in the Grades on the basis of obtained Marks out Of 40

Observation & Data Interpretation:

The values (Performance Levels/Grades) shown in the table and graph are on the basis of Statistical Analysis.

1. Not a single Teacher-trainees performed on Excellent Level in Pre -test but **16 (32.00%)** Teacher – trainees performed very well i.e. Excellent (O Grade)
2. Not a single Teacher-trainee is performed on Good Level in Pre -test but **28 (56.00%)** Teacher – trainees performed very well i.e. Good (A+ Grade)
3. **12 (24.00%)** Teacher-trainees performed in Pre – Test and **5 (10.00%)** were performed on Average Level, So, they comes under A Grade.
4. **15 (37.50%)** Teacher-trainees performed in Pre – Test and **0 (00.00%)** were performed on Satisfactory Level, So, they comes under B Grade. and
5. **23 (57.50%)** Teacher-trainees performed in Pre – Test and **01 (02.00%)** was performed on Unsatisfactory Level, So, they comes under C Grade.

Conclusion :

As per the above data interpretation and on the basis of Table properties and with the help of Graphical presentation , the Programme conducted based on Health, Yoga and Sports activities improved and developed the awareness , knowledge, Understanding, Skills among the teacher-trainees.

- **Data Analysis:** The data analyzed by researcher as follows and presented in Table.:

Table No. 01: Statistical analysis of Observed Values

Statistical analysis of Collected Data through Pre & Post Test to check the effectiveness of activities conducted about Health, Yoga & Sports on B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Test	Percentage (%)	Mean	SD	df.	R	't' Value	Hypothesis Accepted/Rejected
Pre	49.26	24.26	4.927266908	49	0.208428761	2.90245E-20	Null Hypothesis Rejected
Post	70.00	35.08	2.563479778	49			Research Hypothesis Accepted.

**Significant Level: 0.001: Remark: Value of 't' is Significant with the table value, and the Research Hypothesis is accepted.*

Observation & Data Interpretation:

The above table shows the details of the statistical analysis of the scores received from the Test. This test having 40 Marks. Out of 40 Marks, the mean Score of the Pre – Test is 24.26 and mean score of Post Test is 35.08. The 50 Teachers-trainees out of 100 students selected

by the lottery method of Randomized Sampling Method. The Standard Deviation of Pre-test is 4.92 and Post – Test is 2.56. the co-efficient is 0.208 and the ‘t’ value calculated on the 0.001 significant Level is 2.902.

On the basis of above ‘t’- Value (2.90245E-20), with observed ‘t’- value in One tailed Table value chart is significant on 0.001 significant Level. So, the Null Hypothesis is rejected and Research Hypothesis is accepted.

Findings :

1. B.Ed. Teacher – trainees were not so much aware about the benefits of Health, Yoga & Sports activities.
2. The awareness lectures, orientations and activities sessions /Programms are effective to improve their performance in Health, Yoga and Sports activities.
3. The achievement of teacher-trainees in Pos -test was improved comparatively Pre-test.
4. The Programme/activities conducted by researcher, related to Health, Yoga and Sports are useful & effective to develop the awareness, Knowledge, Understandings and Skill among the teacher-trainees.
5. The responses about the programme based on the Health, Yoga and Sports activities found effective and positive for the teacher-trainees.

Conclusion:

The difference between the pre and post-test had proven that, the conducted programme based on the Health, Yoga and Sport activities improved and developed the awareness about the need, importance, roles and responsibilities, knowledge, understanding and skills about the same among B.Ed. teacher- trainee’s. Also, the conducted program found effective on the basis of the Pre and post -tests scores.

So, the conclusion is that, the teacher-trainees are little bit aware about the benefits, importance and understanding the role, responsibilities about how to conduct Health ,Yoga and Sports activities, but after its conduction they improve and perform very well manner, means the program design and its implementation results found very effective.

Suggestions:

1. The Schools and Educational Institutes have need to organize and promote to Heads and theirs teachers for effective organization and its execution.
2. Teacher-trainees should give 100% active participation in such kind of programs/activities and develop their knowledge, understanding, Skills, attitude, interests and develop their own personality as a future teacher also.

References

- Bucher, C. A., & Wuest, D. A. (2010). *Foundations of physical education, exercise science, and sport* (17th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Council of Europe. (2001). *European Sports Charter*. Council of Europe. <https://rm.coe.int/16804c9dbb>
- Feuerstein, G. (2008). *The yoga tradition: Its history, literature, philosophy, and practice* (3rd ed.). Hohm Press.
- Frontiers in Psychology. (2021). *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, Article 621272. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.621272/full>
- Greenberg, J. S. (2021). *Health and wellness* (13th ed.). Jones & Bartlett Learning.
- Hales, D. (2022). *An invitation to health* (19th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- McArdle, W. D., Katch, F. I., & Katch, V. L. (2015). *Exercise physiology: Nutrition, energy, and human performance* (8th ed.). Wolters Kluwer.
- Patanjali. (c. 200 BCE). *The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali* (Translation varies by edition). (Original work published ca. 200 BCE).
- Patanjali. (2003). *The Yoga Sutras of Patanjali* (S. S. Saraswati, Trans.). Bihar School of Yoga. (Original work published ca. 200 BCE).
- Saraswati, S. S. (2001). *Asana pranayama mudra bandha* (4th ed.). Bihar School of Yoga.
- Williams, J. M. (Ed.). (2010). *Applied sport psychology: Personal growth to peak performance* (6th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- World Health Organization. (1948). *Preamble to the Constitution of the World Health Organization*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/about/governance/constitution>
- World Health Organization. (n.d.-a). *Health and well-being*. Global Health Observatory. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/major-themes/health-and-well-being>
- World Health Organization. (n.d.-b). *Sport and health*. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/sport>